

Open Call for HealthTech Innovators & Living Labs

EVOLVE2CARE project accelerates experimentation
and boosts market readiness of Healthcare solutions!

What is it about?!

The Open Call **matches HealthTech Innovators** (startups, SMEs or research teams) with **Living Labs** to test their research results, products or solutions and **take advantage of the real-world Living Labs' infrastructure!**

How it works?!

Find your match at Find your innovation partner

All interested applicants need to first register on the **Accelup platform**, a product of European Network of Living Labs that offers an **online space for wider, simplified, and more efficient access to the best Living Lab infrastructures and their research on demand services.**

Collaborate to boost your chances for success and smooth your path to market!

Once your application is approved you will connect with Living Labs and get to validate your HealthTech solution leveraging up to €5000 worth of services including:

- Access to Data & Infrastructure
- Co-creation
- User Engagement
- Product Validation
- **and more!**

Take note!

Total Open Call budget is €50,000, available through services agreements between the European Network of Living Labs and the participating Living Labs.

Maximum amount per proposal is €5,000, while the exact amount is determined by the Living Labs it may not exceed €5,000.

Opening date: March 17, 2025

***Closing date:** November 6, 2025 17:00 CET

*unless the available budget is fully allocated earlier

Grab your chance to apply!

Scan the QR code to visit the **EVOLVE2CARE Open Call website**, where all the necessary documents, guidelines and step-by-step demos are available!

